

ADORE.software Toolkit

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1. Introduction

The ADORE.software Toolkit aims to support implementation of the [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability](#). It provides examples of funder programs, policies, and resources for each of the Declaration's recommendations in the four areas of research software practice, research software ecosystem, research software personnel, and research software ethics. The Toolkit is a living resource – it will be updated regularly to incorporate new information. Please make additions by contacting info@researchsoft.org.

2. Definitions

Research Software

For the purpose of this Declaration, research software is defined as: “source code files, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows and executables that were created during the research process or for a research purpose. Software components (e.g., operating systems, libraries, dependencies, packages, scripts, etc.) that are used for research but were not created during or with a clear research intent should be considered software in research and not research software. This differentiation may vary between disciplines.” ([Gruenpeter et al., 2021](#), as implemented in [FAIR Principles for Research Software](#) (FAIR4RS Principles).

See also [Defining the roles of research software](#) (van Nieuwpoort & Katz, 2024), and the variety of definitions provided in [What is Research Software? And why is it critical to the research endeavour?](#) (Goble, 2023). [Multi-Dimensional Categorization of Research Software with Examples](#) (Hasselbring, 2024) provides yet another approach.

Research Software Infrastructure

Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) [A National Agenda for Research Software](#) (2022) defines research software infrastructure in relation to other types of software: Software can come in many forms, including scripts, code, notebooks, computational workflows, libraries, modules, frameworks, utilities, and applications. Here we focus instead on what they get built for.

- ANALYSIS CODE - capture research processes and methodology: the steps taken for tasks like data generation, preparation, analysis, and visualisation.
- PROTOTYPE TOOLS - demonstrate a new idea, method, or model for research.
- RESEARCH SOFTWARE INFRASTRUCTURE - capture more broadly accepted and used ideas, methods, and models for research.

Funders

For the purpose of the Declaration, a funder is an organisation that supports research software and/or the people who develop and maintain it. This definition fits traditional funding organisations that provide monetary and/or in-kind support to a recipient on the basis of grants or gifts, without any expectation of services or other tangible benefits from the recipient and typically with limited involvement in project management, operations, and governance. A traditional funder can (and often does) direct that their grant go towards a particular project, outcome, or deliverable, and can (and often does) set conditions on the way the support is utilised (adapted from [Dunks, 2021](#)).

3. Research Software Practice

Introduction

This section provides support on implementing the three recommendations in the Declaration in the area of research software practice.

Recommendations

1. Funders should stimulate the documentation, licensing, open-source distribution, and accessibility of research software to enable the reproducibility of research outcomes.
2. Funders should incentivize the reuse and improvement of existing research software.
3. Funders should include research software in open science policies, following the principle ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’, to ensure it is a valuable and impactful research output.

Examples of funder programs

- Alfred P. Sloan Foundation [Call for Letters of Inquiry: Institutional Support for Open Source Software in Research](#). Focuses on Open Source Program Offices (OSPOs).
- Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) [Platforms Program](#).
- Canadian Network for the Advancement of Research, Industry and Education (CANARIE) [Software re-use in research](#). Enables research teams to evolve their platforms for use by other researchers.
- Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI) [Essential Open Source Software for Science](#) (EOSS).
- CHIST-ERA [Open & Reusable Research Data & Software](#).
- Dutch Research Council (NWO) [Open Science Fund](#).
- [FAIR-IMPACT Route 2 support](#) includes support actions focused on assessment and improvement of research software.
- German Research Foundation (DFG) [Call for Proposals to Increase the Usability of Existing Research Software](#).

- German Research Foundation (DFG) [Research Software Infrastructures program](#) supports the development, establishment, or organisation of research software infrastructures. The program aims to pave the way for the improvement of subject-specific handling of research software while supporting the development of a community-based framework of research software infrastructures in Germany. Proposals are subject to a maximum funding period of three years. The programme is unlimited; as of 2025, proposals can be submitted twice a year, i.e. every March and August (see [guidelines](#) for further details).
- NASA [High Priority Open-Source Science](#). Aims to make science more accessible, inclusive, and reproducible.
- NASA Science Mission Directorate ROSES-24 [E.7 Support for Open-Source Tools, Frameworks, and Libraries \(OSTFL\)](#) solicits proposals for the improvement and sustainment of existing high-value, open-source tools, frameworks, and libraries.
- National Science Foundation (NSF) [Cyberinfrastructure for Sustained Scientific Innovation \(CSS\)](#).
- The National Institutes of Health (NIH) [Building Sustainable Software Tools for Open Science](#).
- Netherlands eScience Center [Call for Sustainable Software](#).
- UKRI's Medical Research Council (MRC) and the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR): [Enhancing biomedical and health-related data and digital platform resources](#). Apply for data and digital platform resources that will support, manage, link, share and access data at scale for biomedical health and care research, including enhancing platforms, environments and their operations; capabilities for users, for example data ingress or egress tools, analytics; and more. Closes 18 June.
- [Software and skills for research computing in the UK](#) on what is needed for the UK to respond to challenges over the next five years.
- [Scientific Software – Klaus Tschira Stiftung](#). Concepts that help to overcome information technology barriers in scientific research, e.g., approaches for better software availability, cooperation between computer centers, assistance from computer science institutes, or further training measures
- The Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) [Research Software Maintenance Fund](#) (RSMF) is a funding initiative offering £4.8 million to support existing research software. The fund aims to improve how research software is maintained and reduce technical debt, ensuring essential tools remain available to the research community.

* Note that the above examples may also address other recommendations

Relevant funder policies

- International
 -
- National
 - [Database](#) of national open science policies - Research Data Alliance (RDA) Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) Interest Group resource.

- [Canada] [Tri-Agency Research Data Management Policy](#). Includes code deposit as a requirement, in addition to data and other outputs; and that grantees have a publicly accessible strategy to support policy around research data/software management per the policy.
- [European Union] European Commission [open science policy](#) and [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#).
- [Finland] [Policy for Open Research Data and Methods](#).
- [Germany] [Handling of research software in DFG's funding activities](#)
- [Ireland] Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) [Open Access Policy](#). SFI encourages that research data and software should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable & Reusable (FAIR). All data, original software, or materials that underpin SFI-funded research publications should be deposited in an open access repository.
- [Italy] [National Plan for Open Science](#).
- [Serbia] The [national open science policy](#) includes requirements for software source code.
- [Slovenia] [Slovenia's adoption](#) of the [Decree on the Implementation of Scientific Research Work](#) and an [Action Plan for Open Science](#) includes commitments to research software.
- [United Kingdom] [UKRI open access policy](#). Includes code and software as part of research data, as defined in the Concordat on Open Research Data.
- Institutional
 - [Model Policy on Sustainable Software at the Helmholtz Centers](#)
 - [Research institution policies to support research software](#) (Research Software Alliance)
 - TU Delft [Research Software Policy](#)
 - Wellcome's [Data, software and materials management and sharing policy](#)
- Disciplinary
 - Belmont Forum [Data Policy](#). Includes consideration of software in the Data Management Plan.

Strategies, guidelines, and recommendations

The following are examples of how to support the recommendation in practice.

- [Australia] [A National Agenda for Research Software](#).
- [Canada] [National Research Software Strategy 2023](#) - [Stratégie nationale en matière de logiciels de recherche 2023](#)
- [European Union] [Scholarly infrastructures for research software \(SIRS\): Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group Architecture Task Force](#). Establishes a set of recommendations to allow the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to include software, next to other research outputs like publications and data, in the realm of its research artefacts.

- [France] French [National Plan for Open Science](#)
- [Germany] German Research Foundation (DFG) - [notes and guidance](#) regarding the handling of research software in DFG-funding activities.
- [Netherlands] [Open Science NL presents the work programme for 2024 and 2025](#), The programme dedicates €6 million to a software sustainability programme, to be implemented by the Netherlands eScience Center; and also invests in building trainer capacity for open source software skills at Dutch public research institutions.
- [USA] NASA Science Mission Directorate (SMD) [Open-Source Science Guidance](#). Includes a section on software management and sharing.
- [USA] Department of Energy (DoE) support for the [Interoperable Design of Extreme-scale Application Software](#) (IDEAS) projects, as well as other significant software investments in its [Exascale Computing Project](#).

Relevant resources

- International standards:
 - OECD [Council Recommendation on Access to Research Data from Public Funding](#)
 - UNESCO [Recommendation on Open Science](#). See also the UNESCO [Open Science Toolkit](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software](#) (FAIR4RS Principles), which were introduced in this [Scientific Data article](#).
 - [FAIR4RS: A summary](#) (Katz et al., 2022)
 - [Five Recommendations for FAIR Software](#) (Netherlands eScience Center & DANS)
 - [What is the value of making research software FAIR?](#) (Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC))
 - [Six Recommendations for implementation of FAIR practice by the FAIR in practice task force of the European Open Science Cloud FAIR working group](#) (European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2020)
- Licensing:
 - The Turing Way Guide for Reproducible Research: [Licensing](#)
 - Software Sustainability Institute: [Choosing an open-source license](#) (Chue Hong and Parkinson, 2021)
 - GitHub: [Choose an open source license](#)
- Open Research Funders Group (ORFG) [Policy Clause Bank](#) includes four policy levels: Level 1 - Encouraging but not requiring code/software sharing; Level 2/3 - Requiring code/software shared, no timing specified; Level 3 - Requiring underlying code/software shared immediately; and Level 4 - Requiring code/software sharing with open licensing.
- [Open Science – Source code and software](#) (French Ministry of Higher Education and Research, 2023). Addresses the particular challenges of opening up the source code and software produced and used in scientific research
- OSPOs:

- [How Can Open Source Program Offices \(OSPOs\) Support Research Software?](#) (Hartley et al., 2023).
- [SustainOSS](#): a community of people who are interested in the sustainability of open source projects and communities.
- [CURIOSS](#): a community that aims to provide support and to build the collective capacity of members who are creating, managing and sustaining Open Source Program Offices in universities and research institutions around the world.
- [Policy recommendations to ensure that research software is openly accessible and reusable](#) (McKiernan et al., 2023) argues that to maximise research equity, transparency, and reproducibility, policymakers should take concrete steps to ensure that research software is openly accessible and reusable.
- [Research software is essential for research data, so how should governments respond?](#) (Barker et al., 2021)
- [Software is Ubiquitous, yet Overlooked](#) (Hocquet et al, 2024).
- [Sustainable research software for high-quality computational research in the Earth System Sciences: Recommendations for universities, funders and the scientific community in Germany](#) (Döll et al., 2023).
- [Tales of Transitions: Seeking Scientific Software Sustainability](#) (Cohoon et al., 2025).
- [Testing Research Software: An In-Depth Survey of Practices, Methods, and Tools](#) by Nasir Eisty et al.
- [We need to talk about the lack of investment in digital research infrastructure](#) (Knowles et al., 2021).
- On the complexity of policies
 - [Landscape of policies around research software](#) (Barker, 2022)
 - [Implementation of policies on research software](#) (Chue Hong, 2022)

4. Research Software Ecosystem

Introduction

This section provides support on implementing the three recommendations in the Declaration in the area of research software ecosystem.

Recommendations

4. Funders should stimulate the development and maintenance of a research software ecosystem, including people, communities, and infrastructure, to ensure research software sustainability.
5. Funders should share information about their investments and work in a coordinated manner, as the research software ecosystem exceeds institutional and national boundaries.

6. Funders should ensure that funding instruments are fit for purpose for both sustainability and innovation, so that research software is both maintained and developed for the longer term, to encourage a healthy research software ecosystem.

Examples of funder programs

- US Department of Energy (DoE) [Seed Collaborations for Software Sustainability](#). The Advanced Scientific Computing Research (ASCR) program seeks to seed collaborations focused on software sustainability.
- US DOE: [Consortium for the Advancement of Scientific Software](#) (CASS) is a US DoE supported organisation dedicated to stewarding and advancing the scientific software ecosystem, focusing initially on the software developed by DOE's Exascale Computing Program (ECP). It is organised to facilitate collaboration and coordination among the member software stewardship organisations to ensure that collectively they can provide broad and consistent support for the stewardship of the scientific software ecosystem.
- European Commission's Horizon Europe Framework Program: Enabling an operational, open, and FAIR EOSC ecosystem includes [Development of community-based approaches for ensuring and improving the quality of scientific software and code](#). Aims to promote quality of software and code across the different disciplines. Activities covered include those that foster alignment of existing initiatives by promoting coherence and developing community guidelines, and ensure integration of infrastructure, tools, and services.
- National Institutes of Health (NIH) Office of Data Science Strategy (ODSS) [Administrative Supplements to Support Enhancement of Software Tools for Open Science](#). These supplements aim to enhance the sustainability and impact of research software tools by enabling the use of best practices and design principles in software development and leveraging advances in computing in a modern data ecosystem.
- Netherlands eScience Center [Open eScience Call 2024](#). Supports state-of-the-art and innovative research that requires the development and application of advanced research software.
- [Sage Concept Grants](#). This program provides funding for innovative software solutions that support research in the social sciences. The grants are designed to fund new technological solutions that support the adoption, development, and application of established and emerging research methods, including quantitative, qualitative, mixed, and computational methods.
- US Networking and Information Technology Research and Development (NITRD) [High End Computing \(HEC\) Software Sustainability Efforts: Examples of Federal Activities](#)
- Multilateral investments:
 - [Research Software Funders Forum](#) Working Group on a multilateral lateral funding call for research software.
 - [G8 Research Councils Initiative on Software Toward Exascale Computing for Global Scale Issues](#) (NSF 10-025) was software-intensive but not software-focused (helped lead to formation of Belmont Forum).

- [European Research Area Networks](#) (ERANETS)
- CHIST-ERA [Open & Reusable Research Data & Software](#)
- [Weave](#), supported by [Science Europe](#), is a bottom-up, cross-European initiative developed by European research funders to support excellent collaborative research projects across borders.
- Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI) [Essential Open Source Software for Science](#) (EOSS) Cycle 6 - in partnership with The Kavli Foundation and The Wellcome Trust.
- [Digital Infrastructure Insights Fund](#) (D//F) is a global multi-funder initiative supported by the Ford Foundation, Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, Omidyar Network, and Schmidt Futures.

*Note that the above examples may also address other recommendations

Relevant funder policies

- The [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) released in 2024 was prepared by a group of over 25 research information experts, representing organisations that carry out, fund, and evaluate research, as well as organisations that provide research information infrastructures. Signatories of the Declaration commit to taking a lead in transforming the way [research information](#), including metadata on software and research information located in systems such as software archives, is used and produced.

Relevant resources

- [Developing and Aligning Policies on Research Software: Recommendations for Research Funding and Research Performing Organisations](#) (Saenen, 2024) makes recommendations to research funding and research performing organisations on developing and aligning policies based on existing good practices and other resources.
- [Directions for Research Software Engineering Research](#) (Barker & Hasselbring, 2024)
- [Funding Open Source Science Software: The state of the open source ecosystem & how to fund away 'software collapse'](#) (Iacovou, 2024).
- [Generating Software Bill of Materials \(SBOMs\) in Scientific Software](#) (Hart, 2024).
- [Investigating Research Software Engineering: Toward RSE Research](#) (Felderer et al., 2025).
- [Metrics for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context](#) (Chue Hong et al., 2023) defines 17 metrics that can be used to automate the assessment of research software against the FAIR4RS Principles, and provides examples of how these might be implemented in one exemplar disciplinary context of the social sciences.
- ReSA [Overview of the research software funding landscape](#) (Barker & Katz, 2022).
- ReSA [database](#) on research software funding calls ([form](#) to submit information).
- [Research software is critical to the future of AI-driven research](#) (Barker et al., 2024).
- Research software sustainability:

- [Software Sustainability Institute](#) (SSI). Sustainability means that the software you use today will be available – and continue to be improved and supported – in the future. Software Sustainability Institute’s [Approaches to software sustainability](#).
- [Defining Software Sustainability](#) (Katz, 2016).
- Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) [Sustaining Research Software](#). Sustaining research software means: identifying pathways to support maintenance; sustaining roles which are themselves stable, inclusive, supported, and valued; and using tools and techniques for building better software.
- [Research software sustainability](#) (Australian Research Data Commons, 2020)
- [Software sustainability and researcher engagement: a conversation with Dr Daniel S. Katz](#) (National Institutes of Health, 2023).
- [Roads and Bridges: The Unseen Labor Behind our Digital Infrastructure](#), with link to report by Eghbal, 2016.
- [Ten simple rules for funding scientific open source software](#) (Strasser et al., 2022).
- [Unearthing research software](#) finds that nearly half of over 13,000 Australian Research Council grants between 2010 and 2019 resulted in research software (Maxfield Brown and Weber, 2024).
- Netherlands [National Research Software Day](#) facilitates engagement with initiatives that boost research software’s important role in the academic landscape, with a focus on community and collaboration. This is a joint initiative of the Netherlands eScience Center, National Coordination Point Research Data Management, Open Science NL and the University of Amsterdam Data Science Center.

Networking opportunities

- [EOSC Opportunity Area \(OA\) Expert Group: Research Software](#) aims to promote all aspects of research software, including metadata, quality, preservation, registries, reproducibility, and recognition. To join, complete this [expression of interest form](#).
- Research Software Funders Forum
 - The [Research Software Funders Forum](#) is a collaboration of funding organisations committed to supporting research software, and those who develop it, as fundamental and vital to research. It provides a formal mechanism for funders to share practices and consider how to address common challenges to achieve the significant cultural change needed across the research sector globally.
- [Science Philanthropy Alliance](#)
 - The Alliance actively works to increase philanthropic reach and support for science by making investments more impactful and results-driven –thereby catalysing scientific discovery for the benefit of society and the planet.

5. Research Software Personnel

Introduction

This section provides support on implementing the three recommendations in the Declaration in the area of research software personnel.

Recommendations

7. Funders should stimulate the training, hiring, and funding of both professional research and technical staff able to reuse, develop, and maintain sustainable research software.
8. Funders should facilitate appropriate reward and recognition measures that enable career progression for all people involved in the creation and maintenance of research software.
9. Funders should require citation practices for research software that recognise substantial contributors to all aspects of the software.

Examples of funder programs

- Advancing Earth and Space Science (AGU) [Open Science Recognition Prize](#). Is awarded to a person or team for outstanding work in advancing Open Science related to Earth and space science and its impact globally. Eligible work can include software.
- Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) [Australian Museum Eureka Prize for Excellence in Research Software](#). This prize is awarded for the development, maintenance, or extension of software that has enabled significant new scientific research. The \$10,000 Eureka Prize for Excellence in Research Software is open to both individuals and teams that include an Australian or Australia-based developer or maintainer.
- [EPSRC and UKRI funding focus on community-driven projects providing training and development for research technical professionals \(RTP\)](#): This £16 million support by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Digital Research Infrastructure recognises that RTPs are vital to the effective operation of research infrastructure across the UK. RTPs use their skills and experience to support academic and industrial research, as well as to train users in the latest techniques and methods. In addition to providing skills to improve their long-term career prospects, the 11 projects will train RTPs in areas including software development.
- [Netherlands eScience Center Fellowship Program 2023](#). Aimed at members of the academic research community who are passionate to act as ambassadors for the use of research software. Research software can be any piece of code, script, package, tool, library, or programme written for the purpose of being used in research. The Fellowship

Programme supports those who want to promote or improve the awareness and use of research software within their institute or academic community.

- The [Netherlands eScience Center](#) and [LCRDM](#) co-organised the first [National Research Software Day](#) on April 23, 2024.
- Open Bioinformatics Foundation (OBF) [Event Fellowships](#). Promotes open source bioinformatics software development and open science in the biological research community. The program is aimed at increasing diverse participation at events promoting open science practices such as resource development and dissemination in the bioinformatics and biological research community. These fellowships are available to support both in-person and remote (virtual) participation at events such as conferences, workshops, training courses, or collaborative development sprints.
- Open Science Netherlands' [Strengthening local and thematic DCCs: Software Training and Data Interoperability](#) aims to strengthen the capacity of local and thematic digital competence centres (DCCs) in the area of research software training and research data interoperability. The expanded software training capacity, brought together in a national network, will help increase the number of researchers and research support staff that can be trained in the area of open research software. The investment in ontology and metadata expertise will help address the data interoperability aspects of the FAIR principles. Local and thematic DCCs, as well as the Netherlands eScience Center, can apply for additional people capacity in this call for proposals. Projects can last max. 4 years.
- [rOpenSci Champions Program](#). This call aims to identify, recognise, and reward passionate members of the R community, including people who belong to groups that are historically and systematically excluded. The [2025 Champions Program](#) is dedicated to supporting leaders in Latin America who work in STEAM fields and have experience with R programming. For the first time, the program will be conducted entirely in Spanish.
- Society of Research Software Engineering (SocRSE) [Events and Initiatives Grant](#). Financial support available for events and initiatives which support establishing a research environment that recognises the vital role of software in research.
- Sovereign Tech Fund [Fellowship for Maintainers](#) pays open source maintainers, aiming to address structural issues and support open digital infrastructure in the public interest.
- Simons Foundation [Scientific Software Research Faculty Award](#). Aims to stimulate the development and maintenance of core scientific software infrastructure in academic environments through creating a new, long-term, faculty-level career path.
- [Software Sustainability Institute Fellowship Programme](#). Provides funding for individuals who want to improve how research software is used in their domains, fields, and/or areas of work.
- UKRI's Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) [strategic technical platform: outline stage](#). Supports strategic investments for systematic support, training, and development to promote, enable, and empower the research technical professional (RTP) community in UK universities.

- UKRI - EPSRC's [Support the development of research software engineering](#). Principal Investigator must be a researcher or Research Software Engineer at an eligible research organisation or an employee of an eligible public sector research establishment.
- UKRI's [Digital Research Technical Professional \(RTP\) Skills NetworkPlus](#) aims to support a small number of Digital RTP Skills NetworkPlus grant awards, led by project leads, which will equitably bring disciplines, sectors, and domains together to: address cross-cutting challenges related to digital RTP skills and careers; provide leadership and coordinate collaborations; seed better ways of working together; and catalyse learning, capability and capacity for digital RTPs. Applications led by research technical professionals – including research software engineers – involved in the delivery of digital research infrastructure, are welcome
- US-RSE [Community and Travel Funds program](#) aims to grow and diversify the US-RSE community and larger Research Software Engineers (RSE) community; connect people within the US-RSE community; assist individuals to grow in their own career; increase visibility and viability of RSE as a career; and create opportunities for underserved community members.
- [NIH Research Software Engineer \(RSE\) Award](#). The funding opportunity aims to provide salary support for exceptional RSEs that contribute their skills to the development and dissemination of biomedical, behavioural or health related software, tools, and algorithms as well as to the training of prospective users of these tools.

*Note that the above examples may also address other recommendations

Relevant funder policies

- Monash University (Business School) policy on [Research Software Standards](#) outlines a process for assessing software in career advancement. Whilst this is a draft, the final policy is in place (but not publicly available).
- TU Delft [Research Software Policy](#) facilitates best-practices on research software management and sharing; emphasises the value of research software as a standalone research output and facilitates proper recognition of the contribution of TU Delft researchers to software, etc. It includes:
 - Best-practices on research software management and sharing, irrespective of whether the code is proprietary or open source.
 - The value of research software as a standalone research output and facilitates proper recognition of the contribution of TU Delft researchers to software.
 - High-level requirements for how software should be managed, the responsibilities of the different stakeholders involved in software development and describes the global workflows that facilitate sharing software openly.

Relevant resources

- [Bridging the gap: Structures for efficiently supporting research software roles and careers at academic institutions](#) (Cohen, 2024).

- [Digital and Professional Skills for Industry: Understanding Employers and Graduates Experiences](#) (Thomas et al., 2025)
- [Encouraging entry, retention, diversity, and inclusion in research software careers](#) (Barker & Katz, 2022).
- [Establishing a national research software award](#) (Blanc Catala et al., 2023) highlights the French national award to promote open-source research software. This award aims to highlight the software projects and teams that have devoted time and effort to develop outstanding research software.
- [FORCE11 software citation principles](#) (Arfon, Katz, & Niemeyer, 2016).
 - The FORCE11 [Software Citation Implementation Working Group](#) builds on the previous [Software Citation Working Group](#), which developed and publicised the initial set of software citation principles.
- [Foundational Competencies and Responsibilities of a Research Software Engineer](#) (Goth et al., 2024) explores educational paths for Research Software Engineers.
- [Hiring, Managing, and Retaining Data Scientists and Research Software Engineers in Academia: A Career Guidebook from ADSA and US-RSE](#).
- Netherlands eScience Center's comprehensive [role description](#) and [job profile](#) for Research Software Engineers.
- [Professionalizing the role of Research Software Engineers in the Netherlands](#) by the National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM) maps the landscape of RSE in the Netherlands, highlighting successful models and persistent barriers. It offers concrete recommendations for RSEs, their organisations, funders, and policymakers to fully integrate RSEs into the academic ecosystem. While focused on the Dutch landscape, the insights are also relevant in an international context.
- [Research Software Engineers: Creating a Career Path—and a Career](#) (US-RSE and the IEEE Computer Society, 2023).
- Research Software Engineering in 2030 (Katz & Hettrick, 2023) - [slides](#), [preprint](#), and [paper](#) provide predictions, including that at least 50 countries globally will have research software engineering associations), and at least one university Masters of Research Software Engineering program will exist; many universities will offer RSE certificates or minors at the undergraduate level
- [Research Software in Academic Hiring and Promotion: A proposal for how to assess it](#) provides a draft that aims to decenter scientific publications as the primary research output that counts, and recommends that published data sets and the development and maintenance of research software are also considered.
- [Senior level RSE career paths \(with an s\)](#) (Katz et al., 2021). Identifies a range of possible career paths.
- [Software and skills for research computing in the UK](#) recommendations include:
 - Enable detailed analysis of how to professionalise RSE roles, building on existing initiatives such as the international RSE survey.
 - Facilitate collaboration between government, funders, and employers to create national policies aimed at improving standards of employment.
- [Ten simple rules for recognizing data and software contributions in hiring, promotion and tenure](#) (Iratxe Puebla et al., 2024) provides advice on areas such as quantitative and

qualitative metrics, and existing tools that provide citation information that can be leveraged.

- [The Value of Stability in Scientific Funding, and Why We Need Better Data](#) (Buck, 2024) about [Scientific Talent Leaks Out of Funding Gaps](#) (Tham et al., 2024)

6. Research Software Ethics

Introduction

This section provides support on implementing the three recommendations in the Declaration in the area of research software ethics.

Recommendations

10. Funders should encourage the responsible use of appropriate indicators to assess the degree of permanence, reusability, and impact of research software.

11. Funders should explicitly consider the environmental and social impact of the use of research software.

12. Funders should explicitly recognise that diversity, equity, and inclusivity are significant factors in making research software sustainable.

Examples of funder programs

- [Digital Research Infrastructure \(DRI\) Equity Champions](#) is a [Digital Research Alliance of Canada](#) initiative with the goal of increasing awareness and uptake of the Alliance's DRI by equity-seeking groups.
- European Commission - Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)'s [Digital and emerging technologies for competitiveness and fit for the Green Deal: Fundamentals of Software Engineering \(RIA\)](#) aims to progress state of the art in responsible software engineering methods, tools, and best practices. Projects are expected to address principles like optimising energy usage, reducing the environmental footprint, security-by-design, and data protection.
- Experiment Challenges (supported by Schmidt Futures, Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation, and Footprint Coalition) [Low-Cost Tools for Science](#). Supports projects that aim to build and/or test new low-cost tools for science. Low-cost science tools can increase access to scientific experimentation and inquiry and encourage innovation by providing individuals and organisations with the resources they need.
- National Science Foundation (NSF) [Strengthening the Cyberinfrastructure Professionals Ecosystem](#). Aims to democratise access to NSF's advanced cyberinfrastructure ecosystem; ensure fair and equitable access to resources, services, and expertise; by strengthening how Cyberinfrastructure Professionals function in this ecosystem.

- [rOpenSci Champion Program Pilot](#): This call aims to identify, recognise, and reward passionate members of the R community, including people who belong to groups that are historically and systematically excluded.

*Note that the above examples may also address other recommendations

Relevant funder policies

- Wellcome Trust's [Environmental sustainability policy](#) outlines how grantees must address the environmental impact of their work. To manage research outputs and reduce wasted resources from duplicated work, researchers should: publish the results of their research (including null results), in line with Wellcome's [open access policy](#); maximise the availability of research data, software and materials with as few restrictions as possible; and manage research outputs in a way that will achieve the greatest health benefit. The policy coincides with the launch of an environmental sustainability concordat from UK research organisations - the [Concordat for the Environmental Sustainability of Research and Innovation Practice](#).

Relevant resources

- [DiveRSE: Supporting equity, diversity, and inclusion within the research software engineering community](#). DiveRSE is a series of talks and related activities including discussion and panel sessions designed to support and raise awareness of equity, diversity, and inclusion challenges and successes within the research software community.
- [Encouraging entry, retention, diversity, and inclusion in research software careers](#) (Barker & Katz, 2022).
- EVERSE's [Research Software Quality Toolkit \(RSQKit\)](#) lists curated best practices, tools and resources for improving the quality of research software
- [Green DiSC is a certification](#) scheme that provides a roadmap for research groups and institutions interested in tackling the environmental impacts of their computing activities.
- [Greener principles for environmentally sustainable computational science](#) (Lannelongue et al., 2023) refers to writing efficient code to reduce carbon footprint and the importance of having trained RSEs within research groups to ensure algorithms used are efficiently implemented.
- Measuring impact of research software:
 - [Awareness of FAIR and FAIR4RS among international research software funders](#) by Eric A. Jensen & Daniel S. Katz
 - [Comparison of tools for automated FAIR software assessment](#) (Antonioletti, et al., 2024) summarises work by the FAIR-IMPACT project to examine the application and potential repurposing of three existing automated assessment tools.
 - [Insights and Impact From Five Cycles of Essential Open Source Software for Science](#) (Hertweck et al., 2024)

- [Mapping the Impact of Software in Science](#) by Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, shares notes from their 2023 hackathon to develop comprehensive datasets, methods, approaches, and resources to map the adoption and impact of research software in science.
- [Towards a Quality Indicator for Research Data publications and Research Software publications – A vision from the Helmholtz Association](#) (zu Castell et al., 2024) This approach amended the FAIR criteria with two additional criteria: scientific quality, addressing the question of research software being scientifically well grounded, and technical competence, capturing aspects of the software being technically well grounded (FAIRST).
- [Large-scale Machine-Learning analysis of scientific PDF for monitoring the production and the openness of research data and software in France](#) (Bassin et al., 2023).
- FAIR-MPACT M5.6 - [Practical tests for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context](#) (Kara Moraw et al., 2024)
- [Reduce, reuse, recycle: save the planet one GitHub action at a time](#) (Smeets & van Rijn, 2023).
- [Prioritise environmental sustainability in use of AI and data science methods](#) (Jay et al., 2024) argues that Artificial Intelligence (AI) and data science will play a crucial role in improving environmental sustainability, but the energy requirements of these methods will have an increasingly negative effect on the environment without sustainable design and use.
- Software Management Plans:
 - [Canada] Digital Research Alliance of Canada - Software Management Plan (SMP) Template ([EN/FR](#)).
 - [Germany] [Software Management Plans – Current Concepts, Tools, and Application](#) (Grossmann et al., 2024).
 - Netherlands eScience Center [definition](#): A Software Management Plan (SMP) helps in deciding how to deal with research software that is being developed as part of projects. It is important to decide which software to keep alive, for how long, and who will be responsible for it.
 - Together with NWO and several Dutch research institutes, the Netherlands eScience Center has developed the [Practical Guide to Software Management Plans](#).
- [Ten simple rules to make your computing more environmentally sustainable](#) (Lannelongue et al., 2021) includes detailed steps for computational researchers and software developers to follow and prioritise to reduce carbon footprints.
- [The Green Software Foundation](#) is a non-profit formed under the Linux Foundation with the mission to create a trusted ecosystem of people, standards, tooling, and best practices for building green software. Resources include [Awesome Green Software](#) and [2023 State of Green Software](#) report.
- [Tracking the environmental impact of research computing](#) (Byrne et al., 2023) - Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) blog post.
- [UKRI Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping Project: Final technical report](#).